

Example Data Management Plan – complete version with full responses

Linking routine data with clinical trial data to determine treatment outcomes from the ZEB34A clinical trial

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Complete version with full responses

Organisation
ELIXIR-UK

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Based on
Based on Standard DMP template for Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BB-SRC) 2024

Funded by the [ELIXIR-UK: FAIR Data Stewardship training UKRI award \(MR/V038966/1\)](#) and [BioFAIR](#)

(Q1) Proposal name

ZEB34A Outcomes: looking at long-term treatment outcome data for the ZEB34A clinical trial participants.

(Q2) Description of the data: Type of study

This study is a data linkage study linking clinical trial participant data with routine death data from the National Trusted Databank (NTD) to determine survival outcomes.

(Q3) Description of the data: Origin of the data

This quantitative study utilises patient identifiers (including date of birth, initials and NHS number) from the ZEB34A clinical trial, coordinated by the University will be used in conjunction with corresponding linked records of these individuals held within the NTD.

(Q4) Description of the data: Types of data

This study utilises clinical trial data captured as part of the ZEB34A clinical trial in conjunction with routine death data from the NTD. The ZEB34A trial was a phase II clinical trial of UK breast cancer patients of approximately 150 participants in total in adults.

Corresponding records for the participants of the ZEB34A trial will be identified within the NTD to determine long-term outcomes of trial participants through linkage to death dates.

(Q5) Description of the data: Format and scale of the data

Data from the ZEB34A clinical trial will be included and comprising:

- **Case Report Forms (CRFs):** collecting data from visits over a six-month period for patients on the trial (n=150). Timepoints include Baseline and eligibility assessments, treatment, one, three and six-month follow up
- **This equates to approximately 15,000 data variables** over the 150 participants, or approximately 20Gb of data stored in csv files.
- **A list of patient identifiers:** (including date of birth, initials and NHS number) from the ZEB34A clinical trial, will be provided by the Clinical Trials Unit (CTU) to the NTD for data linkage purposes. Patient outcome data from the NTD for the trial participants will equate to approximately 1Gb data.

Analyses of the date of death (and thus treatment outcomes) will be performed within the databank and aggregate summary level data will be exported to the University's Research Data Storage Service.

(Q6) Managing, storing and curating data

The ZEB34A clinical trial data is held within the University's Research Data Storage Service (RDSS), a standard activity for CTU. The RDSS department manage ownership and staff access to both the compute and storage systems this project will utilise. This system is resilient, secure and networked storage with on-site and cloud back-up. All data compliant with the UK GDPR and Clinical Trials Regulations and University data handling policies.

Data files will be stored within unique locations within the storage system with consistent naming strategies with access limited to the applicant and associated named members of the trial management team

(Q7) Metadata standards and data documentation

The original data, generated as part of the ZEB34A clinical trial will be accompanied by the original metadata and documentation detailing all coding and analyses conducted by the researchers at the CTU. Analyses performed will match the variable coding to facilitate the ability to correlate with the original trial.

Methodologies for statistical analyses performed will be documented thoroughly. All outputs of this project will be accompanied by appropriate documentation, code commenting and update to resources design for these purposes.

Data files will be stored within unique locations with consistent naming strategies, with access limited to the applicant and associated named members of the trial management team.

(Q8) Data preservation strategy and standards

All data for the ZEB34A data linkage study will be stored as anonymised datasets, and may only be accessed or shared by the CTU in their anonymised format for future research, in compliance with the initial terms of consent by the trial participants.

Document records and data used for secondary analyses are required by the University to be retained for 5 years after the last action is completed in accordance with the BBSRC Statement on Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice.

Data will be stored long-term during the data retention period on the University's Research Data Repository following standard data retention processes for this institution. This facility provides all projects with up to 5 terabytes of storage on the centrally managed Research Data Store. Within this data store, copies of the raw, unprocessed datasets will be stored, plus algorithms and copies of test datasets.

(Q9) Where will data be shared?

Following publication, we will publish the data from this study to the ISRCTN Registry to ensure reusability and accessibility of these findings. Source data will be made publicly available through the UK Data Service. Methodologies, including statistical analyses and scripts and results will be published in open-access scientific journals.

(Q10) When will data be available?

Data will be shared in a timely manner and shared publicly at the time of its publication, or within one year from the project end date. All source data will be made publicly available through the UK Data Service. Methodologies including statistical analyses, scripts and results will be published in open-access scientific journals.

(Q11) How will data be made findable and accessible?

Data from this research will be made available on the ISRCTN Registry, citing the main ZEB34A clinical trial. ISRCTN registry attributes a unique object identification (UOI) number which may be referenced in future citations.

The main results of this data linkage study will be published in a peer-reviewed journal on behalf of all collaborators. The manuscript will be prepared by a writing group that may also include high-achieving clinicians and/or other people who contribute to the trial. All participating centres and clinicians will be acknowledged in this main publication, together with staff from the CTU.

(Q12) How will data be made reusable?

The main study results will be made available to the research community with publication of the full trial methods and results through publication in peer-reviewed scientific journals, presented in a way that allows inclusion in future systematic reviews and on behalf of all collaborators.

Metadata will be prepared to a sufficient standard to enable users to reanalyse the data and understand its origin and use.

(Q13) Restrictions or delays to sharing, with planned actions to limit such restrictions

The primary datasets are under the Data Controllership of the University CTU, whereby the University is designated the Sponsor and data controller.

Access to these primary datasets as anonymised datasets may be accessed through negotiation with the University CTU.

(Q14) Secondary use

This project involves secondary analysis of clinical trial data, and therefore, the subsequent utility of this data may also be limited.

(Q15) Formal information/data security standards

Data provided as part of the initial clinical trial ZEB34A was compliant with the requirements of ICH-GCP and the clinical trials regulations, following all Clinical Trials Unit policies and procedures.

Data will be stored on secure systems with project team access only

(Q16) Main risks to data security

All data available to researchers on this project, whilst being derived from patients, has undergone pseudonymisation by staff within the Clinical Trials Unit and the National Trusted Databank and will be released to the project after satisfying their information security and governance procedures.

Participants of the ZEB34A Trial will only be identified by their initials, date of birth and trial number. Patient identifiers (including date of birth, initials and NHS number) from the ZEB34A clinical trial will be provided by the CTU to the NTD for data linkage purposes. Data linkage team members do not have access to the NHS number.

Data Scientists working on the data will not be members of staff who have access to the pseudonymisation key, and therefore will be unable to re-identify patients as per the UK Data Service End User Licence Agreement.

Data will be stored on compute systems which have been designed by our advanced research computing partners to be ISO27001 compliant and capable of holding data with a Highly Confidential classification. Access to the Data is bound by the UK Data Service End User Licence Agreement, preventing attempts to re-identify individual patients from the dataset.

(Q17) Capabilities

The University provides all projects with up to 5 terabytes of storage on the centrally managed Research Data Store Service to host data for long-term storage in compliance with funding requirements and to allow public access to data where governance and researchers require. The provision of funding throughout the retention period of this data was secured during the funding application and is ring-fenced by the University's Research Data Storage Service to ensure the appropriate retention of the data.

(Q18) Maintaining and implementing the Data Management Plan

This data management plan (DMP) has been produced using the BBSRC template DMP and will be reviewed annually, or in times of change, or if any issues relating to compliance are observed. It is the responsibility of members of the project management team to maintain this DPM as a living document throughout the duration of the research project.

(Q19) Environmental considerations

The University and the National Trusted Databank both hold up-to-date, ISO 14001 certified environmental management system, which has been held continuously since 2012. This covers good practice and continual improvement of the University's environmental aspects, including energy, procurement, pollution, travel, waste, water and biodiversity

(Q20) Responsibilities

All members of the project team (including academic applicants, project partners and appointed posts) will have responsibility for project oversight, data management, metadata creation, data security and data quality assurance, and assisted by other University departments, including information security and Governance.